

Real-world effectiveness and economic evaluations of EMA-approved orphan medicines for spinal muscular atrophy: a systematic literature review

Neli Boseva-Stoyanova¹, Teodora Chamova², Guenka Petrova¹, Alexandra Savova¹

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

² Medical University, Clinic of neurology of the University Hospital Alexandrovska, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Neli Boseva-Stoyanova (124124@students.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 14 April 2026 ♦ Accepted 21 April 2026 ♦ Published 7 May 2026

Citation: Boseva-Stoyanova N, Chamova T, Petrova G, Savova A (2026) Real-world effectiveness and economic evaluations of EMA-approved orphan medicines for spinal muscular atrophy: a systematic literature review. *Pharmacia* 73: e195536. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e195536>

Abstract

Background: Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) is a rare neuromuscular disorder associated with a substantial clinical burden, high supportive-care needs, and a major economic impact. The introduction of disease-modifying therapies (DMTs) has transformed the management of SMA, but questions remain regarding their real-world effectiveness and economic value.

Objective: To conduct a systematic literature review of published studies on the real-world effectiveness and economic evaluations of orphan medicines for spinal muscular atrophy approved within the European Union.

Materials and methods: A systematic literature review was conducted according to a prespecified protocol registered in the Open Science Framework and reported in line with PRISMA 2020 and Joanna Briggs Institute methodologies. PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, and Google Scholar were searched between 16 and 30 May 2025 without date restrictions. Two review components were assessed under one protocol: (1) real-world clinical evidence for approved SMA therapies and (2) economic evaluations of these therapies. After screening and full-text review, 114 real-world evidence (RWE) studies and 19 economic studies met the eligibility criteria; an additional 16 RWE studies and 10 economic studies were identified from gray literature.

Results: A total of 159 studies were included. Across real-world studies, nusinersen, risdiplam, and onasemnogene abeparvovec were generally associated with improved or stabilized outcomes, particularly for motor and respiratory function. The greatest benefits were observed with presymptomatic or very early treatment initiation, whereas in later-treated children and adults, stabilization and slowing of decline were often the most clinically meaningful outcomes. Bulbar and feeding outcomes remained less consistently improved and were reported heterogeneously. Survival outcomes were generally favorable in short- to medium-term follow-up. Economic evaluations consistently showed that treatment cost was the main driver of cost-effectiveness. Most analyses reported incremental cost-effectiveness ratios above conventional willingness-to-pay thresholds, although onasemnogene abeparvovec and presymptomatic treatment scenarios often appeared more favorable. Considerable uncertainty remains regarding the long-term durability of benefit and model assumptions.

Conclusion: In routine practice, DMTs for SMA improve or stabilize important clinical outcomes, with the strongest effects seen when treatment is started early. However, high acquisition costs and limited long-term data continue to challenge cost-effectiveness. More standardized, long-term real-world evidence is needed to strengthen clinical guidance, improve economic models, and support sustainable access decisions.

Keywords

cost-effectiveness, orphan medicines, real-world evidence, spinal muscular atrophy

Introduction

Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) is among the most common rare neuromuscular disorders and is characterized by degeneration of spinal motor neurons, progressive muscle weakness, and functional decline (MedlinePlus 2024; NHS 2024; Boston Children's Hospital 2025). Clinical phenotypes range from severe infantile-onset SMA type 1 to later-onset forms (types 2–4) with longer survival but persistent disability (Munsat 1991; Cleveland Clinic 2024). Reported global incidence is commonly approximated at 1 in 10,000 live births, with carrier frequency estimates approximately one in 50 (D'Amico et al. 2011). Overall prevalence has been estimated at 1–2 per 100,000 individuals (Verhaart et al. 2017).

SMA imposes substantial healthcare and non-healthcare costs driven by chronic supportive care (respiratory and nutritional support, rehabilitation, and assistive technologies) and intensive informal caregiving (Peña-Longobardo et al. 2020). In a multinational European analysis, annual average costs (healthcare and non-healthcare) were approximately €32,000–€54,000 per patient, with most costs attributable to non-healthcare components (79%–86%) (Peña-Longobardo et al. 2020).

The therapeutic landscape has changed rapidly with the introduction of disease-modifying therapies (DMTs), including nusinersen, risdiplam, and gene therapy with onasemnogene abeparvovec (Finkel et al. 2017; Darras et al. 2021; Mercuri et al. 2021). These interventions have improved clinical outcomes in pivotal trials and post-approval studies; however, their high acquisition and delivery costs have intensified questions about affordability and cost-effectiveness in routine practice (Connock et al. 2020; Scheijmans et al. 2022).

Real-world evidence (RWE) complements randomized trial data by capturing effectiveness, utilization patterns, and outcomes in broader patient populations and heterogeneous healthcare settings, where adherence, follow-up, and care pathways may differ from trial conditions (Yeo et al. 2022). Spinal muscular atrophy now has a rapidly growing body of real-world evidence describing outcomes with disease-modifying therapies, complementing pivotal trial data in more heterogeneous, routine-care populations. Across registries and observational cohorts, these data provide valuable insight into the effectiveness, safety, and care pathways in everyday clinical practice.

This study aims to conduct a systematic literature review of published studies on the real-world effectiveness and economic evaluations of orphan medicines for spinal muscular atrophy approved within the European Union and to synthesize real-world economic evaluations of these therapies, including cost-effectiveness outcomes, to support evidence-informed decision-making.

Materials and methods

Protocol registration and reporting

This SLR was conducted according to a prespecified protocol registered in the Open Science Framework (OSF) (osf.io/24s3c; registered 15 May 2025) (Boseva-Stoyanova 2025). The review followed the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology and was reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidance, including documentation of the study selection process in a PRISMA flow diagram (Moher et al. 2009).

Review design and scope

The search strategy comprised two focused components under a unified protocol: (1) real-world use and clinical outcomes of EMA-approved SMA therapies and (2) economic evaluations assessing cost-effectiveness of these therapies. Each component was searched, screened, extracted, and reported separately, with findings summarized together to provide an integrated overview of the clinical and economic evidence.

Eligibility criteria

Eligibility criteria were specified using the PICO framework.

Population

Adult and pediatric patients with SMA of any type (either type 1, 2, 3, or 4), from all geographic locations, in a clinical trial or real-world setting.

Interventions

Any orphan drugs approved by the EMA for SMA.

Comparators

Other orphan drugs approved by the EMA for SMA or standard of care.

Outcomes

Primary outcomes were (1) real-world effectiveness (motor function, respiratory outcomes, swallowing/feeding function, and survival) and (2) cost-effectiveness outcomes (incremental cost-effectiveness ratio [ICER], incremental cost-utility ratio [ICUR], cost per quality-adjusted life-year [QALY], and cost per life-year gained [LYG]).

Secondary outcomes included resource utilization (inpatient and outpatient visits), patient- and caregiver-reported outcomes (e.g., quality of life, patient satisfaction, emotional condition), and policy outcomes (patient access, insurance coverage, and adherence to guidelines).

Additional inclusion criteria were (1) real-world data; (2) cost-effectiveness data; (3) no date restrictions; (4) English-language publications; and (5) full-text availability or sufficient information in the abstract.

Exclusion criteria included editorials and non-systematic reviews, studies without sufficient data on real-world outcomes (for the RWE component), and non-English publications.

Information sources and search strategy

PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, and Google Scholar were searched between 16 and 30 May 2025, without restrictions on the publication year.

Consistent with the two review components, search concepts combined SMA terms (including phenotypes and synonyms such as “5q SMA,” “proximal SMA,” “Werdnig–Hoffmann disease,” and “Kugelberg–Welander disease”) with (a) real-world/observational terms (e.g., real-world evidence/data, observational study, registry data, patient-reported outcomes, post-marketing, effectiveness) for the RWE component, and (b) economic evaluation terms (e.g., cost-effectiveness, cost-utility, cost-benefit, economic evaluation, pharmacoeconomic, economic impact, and health technology assessment [HTA]) for the economic component.

Study selection

After database searching, full texts were downloaded using Zotero software and uploaded to the Rayyan systematic review application and Mendeley Reference Management software to support screening and duplicate removal.

Following de-duplication, one reviewer screened titles and abstracts, and a second reviewer independently screened the same records; disagreements were resolved by consensus, with consultation from a third reviewer when needed. Full texts of potentially eligible publications were then assessed independently by two reviewers, with final disagreements resolved through consultation with the third reviewer. The selection process was documented using a PRISMA flow diagram (Fig. 1) (Page et al. 2021). Following screening and full-text review, 114 RWE studies and 19 economic studies met the criteria. Additionally, 16 RWE studies and 10 economic studies were included after a separate search of gray literature.

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed separately for each component of the review. For RWE studies, extracted data included study design, population characteristics, SMA type, intervention and comparator details, and clinical outcomes such as motor function, respiratory support, quality of life, and survival. For economic evaluations, extracted data included model type, pharmacoeconomic analysis type (e.g., cost-effectiveness analysis and cost-utility analysis), analytic perspective (e.g., societal and payer), effectiveness

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only.

measures (e.g., LYGs and QALYs), and cost-effectiveness ratio values (e.g., ICER and ICUR). Data regarding the prespecified secondary endpoints were extracted by descriptively capturing the reports on healthcare utilization, patient- and caregiver-reported outcomes, and policy outcomes, alongside the observed populations' SMA-specific characteristics. Extracted information was summarized in tabular format, capturing study characteristics (authors, year, country, and design) and results aligned to the prespecified primary and secondary outcomes.

Methodological quality appraisal

The methodological quality of included studies was assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) (Hong et al. 2018).

Ethics

Ethics committee approval was not required for this review of published literature.

Results

Primary endpoints

Motor function

Data on motor function show that DMTs lead to improvement or stabilization, and the effect depends on therapy, age, SMA type, and functional status, as well as the motor scale used. When administered to newborns (type 1), nusinersen promotes a significant increase in the Children's Hospital of Philadelphia Infant Test of Neuromuscular Disorders (CHOP-INTEND) scale ($\approx +6.6$ to $+14.9$ points) and Hammersmith Infant Neurological Examination, Section 2 (HINE-2) scores (Pane et al. 2019; Szabó et al. 2020; De Holanda Mendonça et al. 2021), and early treatment initiation is crucial for achieving milestones such as sitting. In real-world cohorts, the CHOP-INTEND and HINE responder rates reach $\sim 84\%$ (Thomas et al. 2019) and $\sim 90\%$ (Jiang et al. 2024), respectively. In larger registry databases, responder rates of $\sim 67\%$ (CHOP-INTEND), $\sim 63\%$ (Hammersmith Functional Motor Scale Expanded [HFMSSE]), and $\sim 55\%$ (Revised Upper Limb Module [RULM]) at 14 months (Yao et al. 2024) were reported. In non-ambulatory type 2 and 3 patients, improvement/maintenance is observed in HFMSSE ($\approx +4.4$ to $+5.1$ points) and RULM, and $\sim 32.4\%$ reach clinically meaningful improvement in upper limbs (Pechmann et al. 2022). In ambulatory type 3 patients, high responder rates and improvement in the Six-Minute Walk Test (6MWT) were reported (Pechmann et al. 2023a), while in adult patients, the clinically meaningful improvement rates are moderate (HFMSSE ≥ 3 points in 30%, RULM ≥ 2 points in 26%, and 6MWT ≥ 30 m in 48%) (Günther et al. 2024). Risdiplam shows comparable effectiveness in types 2 and 3, with HFMSSE stabilization in 92.3% and improvement

in distal limb motor function (Motor Function Measure, 32-item version [MFM32] scale Subdomain D3) in 66.6% (Bjelica et al. 2024). Meaningful improvement in 6MWT of > 30 m is reported in 22.6% of the Croatian patient cohort (Sitas et al. 2024). Large registry data on onasemnogene abeparvovec show $\sim 95\%$ HINE responders and $\sim 100\%$ CHOP-INTEND responders (Servais 2024). The most favorable results for gene therapy are observed in presymptomatic patients or patients who started treatment very early (Tokatly Latzer et al. 2023; de Albuquerque et al. 2025). In older symptomatic children, the observed effect was not as pronounced (Pane et al. 2023; Gowda et al. 2024). The full list of studies and motor outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S2.

Respiratory function

Real-world data on respiratory outcomes consistently show that DMTs lead to sustained maintenance or a meaningful decrease in respiratory function decline in different SMA types, which are most frequently demonstrated through forced vital capacity (FVC) and adjacent spirometric indicators (De Wel et al. 2021; Pechmann et al. 2022; Krupa et al. 2023; Weiß et al. 2024; Wurster et al. 2024). In pediatric patients, nusinersen slows the annual FVC decline and is associated with clinically meaningful improvement in sleep-breathing indices (e.g., Apnea-Hypopnea Index [AHI]), as the effects are more pronounced with early treatment initiation and longer exposure (Chacko et al. 2022, 2025; Xiao et al. 2023; Trucco et al. 2024). Onasemnogene abeparvovec is associated with high event-free survival (survival without permanent ventilation), including in infants with two SMN2 copies, and favorable thoracopulmonary growth; however, in severe SMA type 1, the need for non-invasive ventilatory support often persisted, with limited change (Desguerre et al. 2024; Servais et al. 2024; Lavie et al. 2025). On the other hand, the risk of initiating or escalating ventilation support can increase with advanced age at treatment initiation and more severe baseline status (Weiß et al. 2024; Lavie et al. 2025). Heterogeneous baseline respiratory impairment is observed across adult SMA types, and although overall FVC remains stable during nusinersen treatment, subgroup analysis shows increased FVC in type 2 and decreased FVC in types 3 and 4 (Wurster et al. 2024). In non-sitter patients ≥ 16 years, risdiplam was associated with improved EK2 respiratory (coughing) scores over 1 year, with no clinically meaningful deterioration (Ñungo Garzón et al. 2023). Substantial subjective gains are also described (improvement in breath fatigue, cough strength, and voice intelligibility), which are not always accounted for by standard objective measures (Ñungo Garzón et al. 2023; Severa et al. 2024; Sitas et al. 2024). Regarding clinical events, a tendency toward a reduction in respiratory-related hospitalizations and hospital stay was observed, although the impact on progression toward mechanical ventilation is not consistent across the study cohorts (Sansone et al. 2020; Cho et al. 2023; Johnson et al. 2023; Krupa et al. 2023). The full list of studies and respiratory outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S3.

Feeding and bulbar function

According to the eligible real-world studies, bulbar and nutritional dependencies often persist, even with motor function improvements. In cohorts treated with nusinersen, the decrease in the need for a nasogastric tube or gastrostomy is not notable, and in certain cases, the probability of tube feeding increases. In symptomatic SMA type 1 patient subgroups, decline of bulbar function is described (Audic et al. 2020; Pechmann et al. 2022, 2023b; Gaboli et al. 2024), although the patient-reported burden on speech and swallowing can appear to decrease (Meyer et al. 2021). In patients treated with risdiplam, including adults with types 2 and 3, studies report clinically meaningful improvement in swallowing, speech, and chewing and subjective functional gain, occasionally accompanied by weight gain (Severa et al. 2024; Sitas et al. 2024). After onasemnogene abeparvovec infusion, most patients included in registries start eating orally, with oral feeding typically maintained in those who were orally fed at baseline. The risk of requiring nutritional support increases with older age and higher weight at infusion, and changes in advanced SMA type 1 can be limited (Pane et al. 2023; Servais et al. 2024; Weiß et al. 2024). The full list of studies and feeding/bulbar outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S4.

Survival

In short- to medium-term follow-up, large real-world cohorts and registries demonstrate high survival rates after DMT (Meyer et al. 2021; Krupa et al. 2023; Yao et al. 2024). Nusinersen treatment leads to marked improvement in survival of severe phenotypes, where long-term exposure in a population-based cohort is associated with a decreased mortality rate (HR 0.05) (Berglund et al. 2022). In large patient registries, including the SMARtCARE Registry Study (SMA Registry Study in Germany and Europe), the overall survival of presymptomatic patients and patients with SMA types 1, 2, and 3 remains high (> 90%) during follow-up periods longer than 36 months (Pechmann et al. 2022, 2023a; Krupa et al. 2023; Servais et al. 2024). The overall mortality rate reported after treatment with onasemnogene abeparvovec is approximately 1.7% in up to 43 months (Weiß et al. 2024), and in the RESTORE registry, the event-free survival (death or permanent ventilation) is reported at 93.7% at 1 year and 90% at 2 years in subgroups with two copies of SMN2 (Servais et al. 2024). Studies with smaller population sizes report 100% survival rates (Malone et al. 2019; Stettner et al. 2023). For risdiplam, direct real-world comparisons in SMA types 2 and 3 do not show statistically significant differences in survival vs. nusinersen in short-term follow-up periods (Ashrafi et al. 2024). The full list of studies and survival outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S5.

Cost-effectiveness outcomes

Cost-effectiveness assessments of SMA disease-modifying therapies differ across SMA types, model structures, and

regulatory bodies, but most studies conclude that high costs frequently result in incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICERs) above standard willingness-to-pay (WTP) thresholds. The predominant type of pharmacoeconomic evaluation in the SLR-eligible studies was a cost-utility analysis (CUA), reporting incremental cost per quality-adjusted life-year (QALY) gained, usually from a payer and health system perspective. Long time horizons were typical, often lifetime or 80–100 years, with models most commonly implemented as cohort Markov state-transition frameworks using motor or respiratory milestones (CADTH 2019, 2021a, 2021b), along with microsimulation (Broekhoff et al. 2021), partitioned survival or multi-state survival approaches (ICER 2019; Dean et al. 2020), semi-Markov structures (Boussahoua et al. 2022), and cost-minimization analyses for head-to-head comparisons (PBAC 2024).

Nusinersen was generally considered not cost-effective compared to best supportive care (BSC), mainly in early-treated SMA type 1. A Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health (CADTH) reassessment reported ICERs of 9.16 million Canadian dollars (CAD) per QALY (type 1), 24.39 million CAD/QALY (type 2), and 7.43 million CAD/QALY (type 3) (CADTH 2019). In the United States (US), the ICER assessment estimated 590,000–1,112,000 USD/QALY for SMA type 1 vs. BSC against a 150,000 USD/QALY threshold (ICER 2019). European ICERs were lower but still often above local thresholds. In Sweden (societal perspective), ICERs were €551,300/QALY (type 1) and €311,800/QALY (types 2 and 3) against a €195,600/QALY threshold (Zuluaga-Sanchez et al. 2019), and in the Netherlands, a microsimulation estimated 647,850 EUR/QALY vs. standard of care with an 80,000 EUR/QALY threshold (Broekhoff et al. 2021). The United Kingdom (UK) National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) conclusions across SMA types 1, 2, and 3 were consistent with these results, evaluating nusinersen as not cost-effective against UK thresholds (NICE n.d.). For adults, the Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee (PBAC) in Australia evaluated an ICER of 1,055,000 Australian dollars (AUD) per QALY for type 1 against the 955,000 AUD/QALY threshold after price considerations (PBAC 2022a).

Onasemnogene abeparvovec tended to yield more favorable cost-effectiveness for SMA type 1 and for presymptomatic treatment, given its one-time dosing, as well as larger modeled survival and milestone gains. In the US, ICER estimated 243,000 USD/QALY for gene therapy vs. BSC against the standard 150,000 USD threshold (ICER 2019), and an updated Markov model estimated 161,648 USD/QALY vs. standard of care against the rare-conditions 500,000 USD threshold but found onasemnogene abeparvovec dominant vs. nusinersen (Dean et al. 2021). In Canada, CADTH estimated 334,090 CAD/QALY vs. standard of care with a 50,000 CAD/QALY threshold and gene therapy dominant vs. nusinersen (CADTH 2021a). In the Netherlands, onasemnogene abeparvovec was estimated at 138,875 EUR/QALY vs. standard of care and 53,447 EUR/QALY vs. nusinersen (Broekhoff et al. 2021), with a WTP threshold

of 80,000 EUR/QALY. Treatment of presymptomatic patients resulted in more favorable results in Italy, an ICER of €90,539/QALY vs. BSC, and dominance vs. nusinersen and risdiplam were reported against an 80,000 EUR/QALY threshold (Valentini et al. 2023), and a presymptomatic analysis in the US estimated 96,977 USD/QALY vs. standard of care against a 100,000 USD/QALY threshold (Jeon and Carlson 2023). In Australia, onasemnogene abeparvovec was reported as dominant vs. nusinersen in the presymptomatic population by the PBAC (PBAC 2022b) and cost-effective vs. BSC by NICE in the UK (NICE 2021a).

Risdiplam showed the greatest dispersion across SMA types and comparators, with unfavorable ICERs for types 2 and 3 in several HTAs. CADTH reported 1.2 million CAD/QALY (type 1) and 37.38 million CAD/QALY (types 2 and 3) vs. BSC at a 50,000 CAD/QALY WTP threshold (CADTH 2021b). A semi-Markov model in a French study estimated 345,217 EUR/QALY (type 1) and 18,000,000 EUR/QALY (types 2 and 3) vs. standard of care but also reported dominance vs. nusinersen (Boussahoua et al. 2022). In contrast to nusinersen, Chinese analyses reported risdiplam as cost-effective, with an ICER of 132,402 Chinese yuan (CNY) per QALY, below the 287,247 CNY/QALY threshold (Huang et al. 2025), and another Chinese analysis reported risdiplam as dominant vs. nusinersen over a 10-year horizon (Hu et al. 2022). In Thailand (societal perspective), ICERs were 158,357 USD/QALY (type 1) and 496,704 USD/QALY (types 2 and 3) against a low local threshold (4,444 USD/QALY) (Khuntha et al. 2025). A short 5-year-horizon Australian submission used a cost-minimization approach and found that risdiplam was cost-saving compared with nusinersen in presymptomatic patients (PBAC 2024), whereas the HTA conclusions of NICE in the UK varied by population—cost-effective in type 1 and not cost-effective in types 2 and 3 (NICE 2021b).

The detailed list of included cost-effectiveness studies is presented in Suppl. material 1: tables S9–S11. To facilitate cross-country comparability, ICERs/ICURs reported in the supplementary tables were converted to EUR (2024 rate) values. These standardized values are presented for comparison only, whereas the interpretation of cost-effectiveness remains context-specific and should be considered in relation to the original study setting, local currency, and applicable willingness-to-pay threshold.

Secondary endpoints

Healthcare resource utilization

Real-world data show high healthcare resource utilization in SMA, but after treatment initiation, a decrease in acute hospitalizations and related costs is observed, especially when the main reason is respiratory issues (Krupa et al. 2023; Reyna et al. 2024). An analysis of insurance claims for nusinersen treatment demonstrated a significant decrease in hospital admissions during the first 12 months (–41% for pediatric patients and –67% for adult patients), accompanied by a cost reduction (–63% to –79%) and lower respira-

tory-related inpatient costs and fewer days after treatment start (Zhu et al. 2024). Nevertheless, long-term care seems to remain the main cost driver (60% of costs in SMA type 1 and 38% in type 2) (Krupa et al. 2023), but the average cost of treating a patient decreased twofold after nusinersen approval. A reduced frequency of hospitalizations is observed after onasemnogene abeparvovec infusion (from 0.8 to 0.5 per patient-year), whereas the need for respiratory and nutritional support usually becomes stable, but the risk of requiring support increases with later treatment initiation and older age at infusion (Dabbous et al. 2023; Weiß et al. 2024). Real-world data for risdiplam indicate that low adherence is related to very high median costs (~\$335,049 difference in type 2 and ~\$41,204 in type 3), mainly due to the more frequent need for mechanical ventilation and feeding support with irregular administration (Patel et al. 2024). Despite the improvements in motor function, severe impairment often persists in patients with SMA type 1, along with the continuous need for respiratory and nutritional support, which maintains the high healthcare resource utilization (HCRU) burden (Pechmann et al. 2023b; Desguerre et al. 2024). The full list of studies and HCRU outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S6.

Patient- and caregiver-reported outcomes

Patient- and caregiver-reported outcomes and quality-of-life data generally demonstrate stabilization or subjective improvement after DMTs, as the impact is strongly dependent on the tool, phenotype, and age. In larger cohorts treated with nusinersen, a high level of satisfaction and global improvement impression is reported by patients and caregivers, including an expressed decrease in perceived fatigue in ambulatory patients with long-term follow-up (Pechmann et al. 2023a) and widely reported subjective improvement after the first year (Cho et al. 2023). In national and multicenter pediatric cohorts, caregivers often assess the clinical status as improved (CGI-I/CGI-I-like measures), frequently exceeding the objective changes in motor scales (Pane et al. 2019; Audic et al. 2020). In adults, treatment is associated with high expectations and trust, and satisfaction is greater in ambulatory patients and correlates with motor function changes (Osmanovic et al. 2021). Patients' goals often include head verticalization, muscle strength, and bulbar function, and improvements are reported precisely in these domains (Duong et al. 2021; Meyer et al. 2021). Improvements in stamina, respiratory function, and trunk stability are reported for risdiplam (Severa et al. 2024; Sitas et al. 2024), and the convenience of oral use is often mentioned as an advantage, accompanied by a positive quality-of-life evaluation (Bjelica et al. 2024). A potential for caregiver burden reduction through achieving new motor milestones and less need for intensive care is described for onasemnogene abeparvovec (Malone et al. 2019). Despite this, for a proportion of the newborns, a decline in parent-reported health-related quality of life (HRQoL) is observed, possibly influenced by higher expectations of the new therapies (Lee et al. 2025). Long-term

observational studies conclude that earlier treatment initiation is key for better patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and functional gains in everyday life not always captured by standard scales (Pechmann et al. 2018; Osredkar et al. 2021; Fainmessenger et al. 2022; Yoon et al. 2024). The full list of studies and patient- and caregiver-reported outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1, S7.

Policy outcomes

Policy and reimbursement decisions are viewed as crucial for access to treatment, healthcare budget sustainability, and tangible clinical benefits from DMTs, with clear intercountry differences in patient eligibility for treatment, funding, and treatment cessation. In Poland, after national reimbursement in 2019, the scope of nusinersen increased to 875 patients until May 2022, and the direct costs for causal drugs reached 51.4 million euro—a testament to both expanded access and high economic burden (Modrzejewska et al. 2021; Krupa et al. 2023). Reimbursement policies in China (National Reimbursement Drug List) and Brazil (Sistema Único de Saúde) also expanded nusinersen access, but essential financial and structural barriers remain. In China, patients continue to cover 25.7% of direct costs, and in Brazil, access for SMA type 2 is often uneven and depends on individual court rulings (de Albuquerque et al. 2025; Zhao et al. 2025). The introduction of neonatal screening (e.g., in Germany and the UK in 2021) is associated with significant time-to-treatment optimization and an opportunity for presymptomatic administration (including gene therapy), which leads to greater functional results as opposed to clinically diagnosed cases (Pechmann et al. 2023b; Gowda et al. 2024; Weiß et al. 2024). Additionally, administrative criteria can limit treatment sustainability in South Korea; approximately 17% discontinue treatment (due to very strict efficacy criteria or switching to a different mechanism of action) (Cho et al. 2023), and in other countries, changing rules and staged access are observed (e.g., criteria changes and later risdiplam approval after compassionate use) (Belančić et al. 2023; Sitas et al. 2024). Interpretation of policy outcomes is limited by incomparability between healthcare systems and the varying quality and completeness of national data. The full list of studies and policy outcomes is provided in Suppl. material 1: tables S1 and S8.

Discussion

This systematic literature review synthesized real-world evidence (RWE) and published economic evaluations for EMA-approved disease-modifying therapies (DMTs) for spinal muscular atrophy (SMA): nusinersen, risdiplam, and onasemnogene abeparvovec. Three consistent messages emerged across the evidence base: earlier treatment delivers the largest functional and survival gains; in later-treated patients, stabilization and slowing decline are clinically meaningful outcomes; and treatment price is the dominant determinant of cost-effectiveness.

Across registries and observational cohorts, outcomes depended mainly on age at treatment start, SMA severity, and baseline function. In presymptomatic infants and very early symptomatic SMA type 1, DMTs more often help patients reach milestones and maintain respiratory stability, reflecting the time-sensitive loss of motor neurons. In older children and adults with established weakness, real-world data more commonly show stabilization or small gains, reinforcing that preserving function and independence are often the most realistic treatment goals.

The strong effect of treatment timing observed across real-world cohorts also has important implications for newborn screening (NBS) programs for SMA. Because disease-modifying therapies are most effective when initiated presymptotically or very early in the disease course, several countries have introduced or are evaluating neonatal screening to enable earlier diagnosis and treatment initiation. Evidence from screening programs shows that infants identified through NBS and treated before symptom onset achieve substantially better motor and survival outcomes compared with those diagnosed after clinical presentation (De Vivo et al. 2019; Vill et al. 2021). From a health-economic perspective, earlier treatment enabled by screening may also improve the cost-effectiveness of high-cost therapies by increasing the likelihood of achieving major motor milestones, reducing long-term complications, and lowering the need for supportive care (Shih et al. 2021). Although newborn screening was outside the predefined intervention scope of this review—which focused on EMA-approved disease-modifying therapies—these findings reinforce the clinical and economic importance of early identification strategies that allow timely initiation of treatment (Dangouloff et al. 2021).

Interpretation is complicated by measurement heterogeneity. Motor scales are not interchangeable and can show floor and ceiling effects, and studies use different definitions of “responders” and meaningful change. Respiratory outcomes are frequently assessed with spirometry, but ventilation status and respiratory events are defined inconsistently, and several cohorts report patient-perceived improvements (e.g., fatigue, cough effectiveness, and voice) that are not always reflected in standard spirometry.

Bulbar and nutritional outcomes remain relatively understudied despite their major impact on morbidity, caregiver burden, and quality of life. Available real-world evidence suggests that dysphagia, speech problems, and the need for feeding support often persist—especially in later-treated patients and with more advanced disease. Reported improvements are difficult to compare because assessments are heterogeneous and sometimes nonstandardized. Stronger evidence will require standardized, sensitive tools and consistent reporting of swallowing, speech, oral intake, and nutritional status.

Linking clinical outcomes to economic value depends on how models convert functional change into QALYs and future costs. Most cost-effectiveness models are driven by motor milestones, ventilation status, and survival. Therefore, the observed real-world early gains in

early-treated patients vs. later stabilization in later-treated patients should be captured using registry-informed transition rates and utilities that capture preserved function, avoided complications, and caregiver time. Additionally, more robust real-world data on standardized bulbar outcomes and long-term supportive care would improve both clinical interpretation and economic credibility.

Across countries, most economic evaluations reach the conclusion that drug price is the main driver of cost-effectiveness and often matters more than differences in clinical benefit, especially in symptomatic SMA types 2 and 3, where improvements are slower. One-time gene therapy and presymptomatic treatment often appear more cost-effective, but results depend heavily on assumptions about long-term durability and the lack of long follow-up data. Interpretation is also limited by differences in patient cohorts, endpoint definitions, and supportive care. This highlights the need for long-term, standardized real-world evidence and for pricing and reimbursement approaches that link healthcare expenditure to outcomes achieved.

Implications for future research

To better support clinical and reimbursement decision-making, future research should prioritize the development of long-term, harmonized registries with follow-up extending beyond 5–10 years that capture treatment sequences, including therapy switching, and adherence in routine clinical practice. Greater emphasis is also needed on standardizing endpoint definitions, particularly by establishing clinically meaningful change thresholds for motor scales and using consistent categories for ventilation status and feeding support. In addition, bulbar and nutritional function should be evaluated more rigorously through sensitive, validated instruments, with consistent reporting of swallowing safety, speech intelligibility, oral intake, and nutritional status. Robust patient- and caregiver-reported outcomes are essential, including SMA-relevant quality-of-life measures and utilities suitable for cost-utility modeling, alongside systematic assessment of caregiver burden and time costs. Finally, high-quality real-world data on resource use and costs under current standards of care—encompassing both healthcare and non-healthcare components—are needed to inform economic model inputs and to test assumptions regarding long-term durability and value.

Conclusion

In routine clinical practice, EMA-approved DMTs for SMA are associated with improved or stabilized outcomes across motor and respiratory domains, with the greatest benefits observed when therapy is initiated presymptomatically or very early. Bulbar and feeding outcomes remain comparatively less responsive and are challenging to measure consistently, representing an important unmet need in both care and research. Despite

life-changing clinical effectiveness results, published economic evaluations frequently find that cost-effectiveness is challenged by high treatment costs and uncertainty around long-term benefit durability. Strengthening long-term real-world evidence will be essential to improve clinical guidance, refine economic models, and support fair and sustainable access policies.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Maria Kamusheva for her valuable contribution to this article.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author Neli Boseva-Stoyanova is an employee of Amgen. The research was conducted independently and without the use of Amgen data, funding, or materials. The views expressed are those of the author and do not necessarily represent the views of Amgen.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This study is financed by the European Union Next-GenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No. BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Neli Boseva-Stoyanova <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3844-5785>

Guenka Petrova <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8116-5138>

Alexandra Savova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4579-5524>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

References

- Ashrafi MR, Babae M, Hashemi Nazari SS, Barzegar M, Ghazavi M, Beiraghi Toosi M, Nafissi S, Inaloo S, Zamani Ghaletaki G, Fatehi F, Heshmat R, Ghahvechi Akbari M, Abdi A, Bakhtiari H, Montazerlotfelahi H, Abbaskhanian A, Hosseini SA, Farshadmoghadam H, Hosseiny SMM, Shariatmadari F, Ziaadini B, Babaei M, Tavasoli A, Nikbakht S, Momen A, Khajeh A, Aminzadeh V, Mollamohammadi M, Taghdiri MM, Nasehi MM, Memarian S, Badv RS, Heidari M, Jafari N (2024) Comparative efficacy of risdiplam and nusinersen in Type 2 and 3 spinal muscular atrophy patients: A cohort study using real-world data. *Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases* 11: 1190–1199. <https://doi.org/10.1177/22143602241288087>
- Audic F, De La Banda MGG, Bernoux D, Ramirez-Garcia P, Durigneux J, Barnerias C, Isapof A, Cuisset JM, Cancès C, Richelme C, Vuillerot C, Laugel V, Ropars J, Altuzarra C, Espil-Taris C, Walther-Louvier U, Sabouraud P, Chouchane M, Vanhulle C, Trommsdorff V, Pervillé A, Testard H, Lagrue E, Sarret C, Avicé AL, Beze-Beyrie P, Pauly V, Quijano-Roy S, Chabrol B, Desguerre I (2020) Effects of nusinersen after one year of treatment in 123 children with SMA type 1 or 2: A French real-life observational study. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 15: 148. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-020-01414-8>
- Belančić A, Strbad T, Kučan Štiglić M, Vitezić D (2023) Effectiveness of nusinersen in type 1, 2 and 3 spinal muscular atrophy: Croatian real-world data. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 12(8): 2839. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12082839>
- Berglund A, Berkö S, Lampa E, Sejersen T (2022) Survival in patients diagnosed with SMA at less than 24 months of age in a population-based setting before, during and after introduction of nusinersen therapy. Experience from Sweden. *European Journal of Paediatric Neurology* 40: 57–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpn.2022.07.005>
- Bjelica B, Wohnrade C, Cespedes I, Osmanovic A, Schreiber-Katz O, Petri S (2024) Risdiplam therapy in adults with 5q-SMA: observational study on motor function and treatment satisfaction. *BMC Neurology* 24: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-024-03562-x>
- Boseva-Stoyanova N (2025) Real-world use and cost-effectiveness of orphan drugs for spinal muscular atrophy: protocol of a systematic literature review. [osf.io/24s3c, February 14, 2026]
- Boston Children's Hospital (2025) Spinal Muscular Atrophy (SMA) | Boston Children's Hospital. <https://www.childrenshospital.org/conditions/spinal-muscular-atrophy-sma> [June 10, 2025]
- Boussahoua M, Sutherland C, Aponte Ribero V, Enache R, Le Lay K, Le Dissez C, Chevalier J (2022) EE173 cost-effectiveness of risdiplam for patients with types 1 - 3 spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) in france-cost-effectiveness of risdiplam for patients with types 1 - 3 spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) in France. *Value in Health* 25: S87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2022.09.423>
- Broekhoff TF, Sweegers CCG, Krijkamp EM, Mantel-Teeuwisse AK, Leufkens HGM, Goettsch WG, Vreman RA (2021) Early cost-effectiveness of onasemnogene abeparvovec-xioi (Zolgensma) and nusinersen (Spinraza) treatment for spinal muscular atrophy I in the netherlands with relapse scenarios. *Value in Health* 24: 759–769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2020.09.021>
- CADTH (2019) CADTH Common Drug Review Version: Final (With Redactions) CADTH Common Drug Review Pharmacoeconomic Review Report (Resubmission) Nusinersen (Spinraza).
- CADTH (2021a) CADTH Drug Reimbursement Review Pharmacoeconomic Report Onasemnogene Abeparvovec (Zolgensma).
- CADTH (2021b) CADTH Reimbursement Recommendation Risdiplam (Evrysdi). <https://www.cda-amc.ca/sites/default/files/DRR/2021/SR0661%20Evrysdi%20Recommendation%20Final.pdf> [October 14, 2025]
- Chacko A, Sly PD, Ware RS, Begum N, Deegan S, Thomas N, Gauld LM (2022) Effect of nusinersen on respiratory function in paediatric spinal muscular atrophy types 1–3. *Thorax* 77: 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1136/thoraxjnl-2020-216564>
- Chacko A, Sly PD, Ware RS, Dyer B, Deegan S, Thomas N, Gauld LM (2025) Differential respiratory function response in paediatric spinal muscular atrophy types 2 and 3 treated with nusinersen over 3 years. *Sleep Medicine* 129: 354–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2025.02.034>
- Cho J, Lee J, Kim J, Lee H, Kim MJ, Lee YJ, Yum MS, Byun JH, Lee CG, Lee YM, Lee J, Chae JH (2023) Nusinersen demonstrates effectiveness in treating spinal muscular atrophy: findings from a three-year nationwide study in Korea. *Frontiers in Neurology* 14: 1294028. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2023.1294028>
- Cleveland Clinic (2024) SMA (Spinal Muscular Atrophy): What It Is, Symptoms & Types. <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/14505-spinal-muscular-atrophy-sma> [June 10, 2025]
- Connock M, Andronis L, Auguste P, Dussart C, Armoiry X (2020) Will the US\$ million onasemnogene abeparvovec treatment for spinal muscular atrophy represent 'value for money' for the NHS? A rapid inquiry into suggestions that it may be cost-effective. *Expert Opinion on Biological Therapy* 20: 823–827. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14712598.2020.1772747>
- Dabbous O, LaMarca N, Toro W, Wallach S, Mumneh N, Aassi M, O'Brien E, Baranello G, Reyna S (2023) P79 Real-world outcomes of disease-modifying treatment for patients with spinal muscular atrophy: findings from a global retrospective chart review. *Neuromuscular Disorders* 33: S136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nmd.2023.07.281>
- de Albuquerque ALA, Chadanowicz JK, Bevilacqua IP, Staub ALP, Winckler PB, da Silva PZ, Fagundes SC, Ferrari RS, Trojahn CD de O, Sacharuk VZ, Kowalski TW, Donis KC, Becker MM, Sautte JAM (2025) Clinicogenetic characterization and response to disease-modifying therapies in spinal muscular atrophy: real-world experience from a reference center in Southern Brazil. *Jornal de Pediatria* 101: 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpmed.2024.07.011>
- D'Amico A, Mercuri E, Tiziano FD, Bertini E (2011) Spinal muscular atrophy. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 6: 71. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1750-1172-6-71>
- Dangouloff T, Vrščaj E, Servais L, Osredkar D, Adoukonou T, Aryani O, Barisic N, Bashiri F, Bastaki L, Benitto A, Omran TB, Bernert G, Bertini E, Borde P, Born P, Boustani RM, Butoianu N, Castiglioni C, Catibusic F, Chan S, Chien YH, Christodoulou K, Dejsuphong D, Farrar M, Filip D, Goemans N, Guinhouya K, Haberlova J, Hadzsiev K, Hovhannesian K, Isohanni P, Radovic NI, Jacquier D, Jalloh A, Jedrzejska M, Kandawasvika G, Kaputu C, Kawatu N, Kernohan K, Kirschner J, Klink B, Kody S, Kouame-Assouan AE, Kravljanc R, Kreile M, Litvinenko I, McMillan H, Mesa S, Mohamed I, Kanzoska LM, Nevo Y, Nguefack S, Nkole K, O'Grady G, O'Rourke D, Oskoui M, Piazzon F, Poddighe D, Prasauskiene A, Prieto J, Rasmussen M, Razafindrasata S, Saha N, Saito K, Sakadi F, Sangare M, Schroth M, Shalkevich L, Shatillo A, Suthar R, Szabo L, Tishvili N, Tazir M, Tizzano E, Topaloglu H, Tulinius M, van der Pol L, Vazquez G,

- Vlodavets D, Wanigasinghe J, Wilmschurst J, Xiong H, Zafeiriou D, Zamba E (2021) Newborn screening programs for spinal muscular atrophy worldwide: Where we stand and where to go. *Neuromuscular Disorders* 31: 574–582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nmd.2021.03.007>
- Darras BT, Masson R, Mazurkiewicz-Beldzińska M, Rose K, Xiong H, Zanoteli E, Baranello G, Bruno C, Vlodavets D, Wang Y, El-Khairi M, Gerber M, Gorni K, Khwaja O, Kletzl H, Scalco RS, Fontoura P, Servais L (2021) Risdiplam-treated infants with type 1 spinal muscular atrophy versus historical controls. *New England Journal of Medicine* 385: 427–435. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2102047>
- Dean R, Miller B, Arjunji R, Awano H, Igarashi A, Tanaka S, Feltner DE, Sproule DM, Jensen I, Dabbous O (2020) PMU36 cost-utility analysis of single dose gene-replacement therapy for spinal muscular atrophy type 1 compared to chronic nusinersen treatment in Japan. *Value in Health* 23: S239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2020.04.810>
- Dean R, Jensen I, Cyr P, Miller B, Maru B, Sproule DM, Feltner DE, Wiesner T, Malone DC, Bischof M, Toro W, Dabbous O (2021) An updated cost-utility model for onasemnogene abeparvovec (Zolgensma®) in spinal muscular atrophy type 1 patients and comparison with evaluation by the Institute for Clinical and Effectiveness Review (ICER). *Journal of Market Access and Health Policy* 9(1): 1889841. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20016689.2021.1889841>
- Desguerre I, Barrois R, Audic F, Barnerias C, Chabrol B, Davion JB, Durigneux J, Espil-Taris C, Gomez-Garcia de la Banda M, Guichard M, Isapof A, Nougues MC, Laugel V, Le Goff L, Mercier S, Pervillé A, Richelme C, Thibaud M, Sarret C, Schweitzer C, Testard H, Trommsdorff V, Vanhulle C, Walther-Louvier U, Altuzarra C, Chouchane M, Ropars J, Quijano-Roy S, Cancas C (2024) Real-world multidisciplinary outcomes of onasemnogene abeparvovec monotherapy in patients with spinal muscular atrophy type 1: experience of the French cohort in the first three years of treatment. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 19: 344. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-024-03326-3>
- De Vivo DC, Bertini E, Swoboda KJ, Hwu WL, Crawford TO, Finkel RS, Kirschner J, Kuntz NL, Parsons JA, Ryan MM, Butterfield RJ, Topaloglu H, Ben-Omran T, Sansone VA, Jong YJ, Shu F, Staropoli JF, Kerr D, Sandrock AW, Stebbins C, Petrillo M, Braley G, Johnson K, Foster R, Gheuens S, Bhan I, Reyna SP, Fradette S, Farwell W (2019) Nusinersen initiated in infants during the presymptomatic stage of spinal muscular atrophy: Interim efficacy and safety results from the Phase 2 NURTURE study. *Neuromuscular Disorders* 29: 842–856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nmd.2019.09.007>
- De Wel B, Goosens V, Sobota A, Van Camp E, Geukens E, Van Kerschaver G, Jagut M, Claes K, Claeys KG (2021) Nusinersen treatment significantly improves hand grip strength, hand motor function and MRC sum scores in adult patients with spinal muscular atrophy types 3 and 4. *Journal of Neurology* 268: 923–935. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-020-10223-9>
- Duong T, Wolford C, McDermott MP, Macpherson CE, Pasternak A, Glanzman AM, Martens WB, Kichula E, Darras BT, De Vivo DC, Zolkipli-Cunningham Z, Finkel RS, Zeineh M, Wintermark M, Sampson J, Hagerman KA, Young SD, Day JW (2021) Nusinersen treatment in adults with spinal muscular atrophy. *Neurology: Clinical Practice* 11: E317–E327. <https://doi.org/10.1212/CPJ.0000000000001033>
- Fainmesser Y, Drory VE, Ben-Shushan S, Lavon A, Spector L, Abramovich B, Abraham A (2022) Longer-term follow-up of nusinersen efficacy and safety in adult patients with spinal muscular atrophy types 2 and 3. *Neuromuscular Disorders* 32: 451–459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nmd.2022.04.003>
- Finkel RS, Mercuri E, Darras BT, Connolly AM, Kuntz NL, Kirschner J, Chiriboga CA, Saito K, Servais L, Tizzano E, Topaloglu H, Tulinus M, Montes J, Glanzman AM, Bishop K, Zhong ZJ, Gheuens S, Bennett CF, Schneider E, Farwell W, Vivo DC De (2017) Nusinersen versus sham control in infantile-onset spinal muscular atrophy. *New England Journal of Medicine* 377: 1723–1732. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1702752>
- Gaboli M, López Lobato M, Valverde Fernández J, Ferrand Ferri P, Rubio Pérez E, Andrade Ruiz HA, López-Puerta González JM, Madruga-Garrido M (2024) Effect of nusinersen on respiratory and bulbar function in children with spinal muscular atrophy: Real-world experience from a single center. *Neuropediatrics* 56: 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-2379-7069>
- Gowda V, Atherton M, Murugan A, Servais L, Sheehan J, Standing E, Manzur A, Scoto M, Baranello G, Munot P, McCullagh G, Willis T, Tirupathi S, Horrocks I, Dhawan A, Eyre M, Vanegas M, Fernandez-Garcia MA, Wolfe A, Pinches L, Illingworth M, Main M, Abbott L, Smith H, Milton E, D'Urso S, Vijayakumar K, Marco SS, Warner S, Reading E, Douglas I, Muntoni F, Ong M, Majumdar A, Hughes I, Jungbluth H, Wraige E (2024) Efficacy and safety of onasemnogene abeparvovec in children with spinal muscular atrophy type 1: real-world evidence from 6 infusion centres in the United Kingdom. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* 37: 100817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanep.2023.100817>
- Günther R, Wurster CD, Brakemeier S, Osmanovic A, Schreiber-Katz O, Petri S, Uzelac Z, Hiebeler M, Thiele S, Walter MC, Weiler M, Kessler T, Freigang M, Lapp HS, Cordts I, Lingor P, Deschauer M, Hahn A, Martakis K, Steinbach R, Ilse B, Rödiger A, Bellut J, Nentwich J, Zeller D, Muhandes MT, Baum T, Koch JC, Schrank B, Fischer S, Hermann A, Kamm C, Naegel S, Mensch A, Weber M, Neuwirth C, Lehmann HC, Wunderlich G, Stadler C, Tomforde M, George A, Groß M, Pechmann A, Kirschner J, Türk M, Schimmel M, Bernert G, Martin P, Rauscher C, Meyer Zu Hörste G, Baum P, Löscher W, Flotats-Bastardas M, Köhler C, Probst-Schendzielorz K, Goldbach S, Schara-Schmidt U, Müller-Felber W, Lochmüller H, Von Velsen O, Study Group S, Kleinschnitz C, Ludolph AC, Hagenacker T (2024) Long-term efficacy and safety of nusinersen in adults with 5q spinal muscular atrophy: a prospective European multinational observational study. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* 39: 100862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanep.2024.100862>
- De Holanda Mendonça R, Jorge Polido G, Ciro M, Jorge Fontoura Solla D, Conti Reed U, Zanoteli E (2021) Clinical Outcomes in Patients with Spinal Muscular Atrophy Type 1 Treated with Nusinersen. *Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases* 8: 217–224. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JND-200533>
- Hong QN, Fàbregues S, Bartlett G, Boardman F, Cargo M, Dagenais P, Gagnon M-P, Griffiths F, Nicolau B, O' Cathain A, Rousseau M-C, Vedel I, Pluye P (2018) The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) version 2018 for information professionals and researchers. *Education for Information* 34: 285–291. <https://doi.org/10.3233/EFI-180221>
- Hu J, Sutherland C, Aponte Ribero V, Zhu L, Hou X, Xia Y, Tang M, Jin C, Kang Q (2022) POSC94 cost-effectiveness of risdiplam versus nusinersen for treating patients with spinal muscular atrophy type 1 in China. *Value in Health* 25: S105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2021.11.499>
- Huang Y, Yuan H, Huang Z (2025) Cost-effectiveness analysis of risdiplam and nusinersen for the treatment of chinese patients with spinal

- muscular atrophy. *Expert Review of Pharmacoeconomics & Outcomes Research* 25: 943–953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14737167.2025.2499720>
- ICER (2019) ICER Spinraza® and Zolgensma® for Spinal Muscular Atrophy: Effectiveness and Value. Final Evidence Report. <https://icer-review.org/programs/new-england-cepac/>
- Jeon Y, Carlson JJ (2023) EE175 Cost-Effectiveness of Onasemnogene in Pre-Symptomatic Newborns with a Diagnosis of Spinal Muscular Atrophy and Two Copies of Survival Motor Neuron 2 Gene. *Value in Health* 26: S91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2023.03.476>
- Jiang Y, Wang Y, Xiong H, Li W, Luo R, Chen W, Yin F, Lü J, Liang J, Chen WJ, Lu X, Wang H, Tang J, Monine M, Makepeace C, Jin X, Foster R, Chin R, Berger Z (2024) A Post-Marketing Surveillance Study of Nusinersen for Spinal Muscular Atrophy in Routine Medical Practice in China: Interim Results. *Advances in Therapy* 41: 2743–2756. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12325-024-02852-7>
- Johnson N, Youn B, Zhu C, Raynaud S, Paradis AD, Ajmani V, Cao Z, Lopes G (2023) CO176 Spinal Muscular Atrophy (SMA) Disease-Related Complications Decreased Over Time after Start of Nusinersen Treatment. *Value in Health* 26: S48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2023.03.2312>
- Khuntha S, Prawjaeng J, Ponragdee K, Sanmaneechai O, Srinonprasert V, Leelahavarong P (2025) Onasemnogene abeparvec gene therapy and risdiplam for the treatment of spinal muscular atrophy in Thailand: A cost-utility analysis. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy* 23: 277–290. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-024-00915-y>
- Krupa D, Czech M, Chudzyńska E, Koń B, Kostera-Pruszczyk A (2023) Real world evidence on the effectiveness of nusinersen within the national program to treat spinal muscular atrophy in Poland. *Healthcare (Switzerland)* 11(10): 1515. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11101515>
- Lavie M, Rochman M, Armoni Domany K, Golan Tripto I, Beër M, Besor O, Sagi L, Aharoni S, Ginsberg M, Noyman I, Levine H (2025) Respiratory outcomes of onasemnogene abeparvec treatment for spinal muscular atrophy: national real-world cohort study. *European Journal of Pediatrics* 184: 58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00431-024-05886-9>
- Lee YJ, Bae H, Shim YK, Cho JS, Chae JH, Kwon S (2025) Impact of nusinersen on the health-related quality of life and caregiver burden in patients with spinal muscular atrophy with symptom onset before the age of 6 months. *Annals of Child Neurology* 33: 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.26815/acn.2024.00668>
- Malone DC, Arjunji R, Dean R, Sproule DM, Feltner DE, Droege M, Khan F, Maru B, Jensen I, Dabbous O (2019) PBI1 the value of onasemnogene abeparvec (AVXS-101) as a cost-effective gene replacement therapy for spinal muscular atrophy type 1 in improving survival, healthcare resource utilization, and motor function. *Value in Health Regional Issues* 19: S11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vhri.2019.08.057>
- MedlinePlus (2024) Spinal muscular atrophy: MedlinePlus Genetics. <https://medlineplus.gov/genetics/condition/spinal-muscular-atrophy/> [June 10, 2025]
- Mercuri E, Muntoni F, Baranello G, Masson R, Boespflug-Tanguy O, Bruno C, Corti S, Daron A, Deconinck N, Servais L, Straub V, Ouyang H, Chand D, Tauscher-Wisniewski S, Mendonca N, Lavrov A, Seferian A, De Lucia S, Tachibana S, Jollet A, Mouffak S, Pedemonte M, Brolatti N, Morando S, Vanlander A, De Vos E, Tahon V, Govoni A, Magri F, Comi G, Foa M, Parente V, Buscemi L, Dal Farra F, Schneider O, Jonas A, Defeldre AC, Pagliano E, Zanin R, Arnoldi MT, Schembri V, Del Sole M, Mandelli A, Pera MC, Antonaci L, Coratti G, de Sanctis R, Pane M, Scoto M, Groves K, Edel L, Abel F, Van Ruiten H, Lofra RM, Thompson E (2021) Onasemnogene abeparvec gene therapy for symptomatic infantile-onset spinal muscular atrophy type 1 (STRIVE-EU): an open-label, single-arm, multicentre, phase 3 trial. *The Lancet Neurology* 20: 832–841. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(21\)00251-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00251-9)
- Meyer T, Maier A, Uzelac Z, Hagenacker T, Günther R, Schreiber-Katz O, Weiler M, Steinbach R, Weyen U, Koch JC, Kettemann D, Norden J, Dorst J, Wurster C, Ludolph AC, Stolte B, Freigang M, Osmanovic A, Petri S, Grosskreutz J, Rödiger A, Griep R, Gaudlitz M, Walter B, Münch C, Spittel S (2021) Treatment expectations and perception of therapy in adult patients with spinal muscular atrophy receiving nusinersen. *European Journal of Neurology* 28: 2582–2595. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ene.14902>
- Modrzejewska S, Kotulska K, Kopyta I, Gredowska E, Emich-Widera E, Tomaszek K, Paprocka J, Chmielewski D, Pilch J, Pietruszewski J, Lemska A, Zawadzka M, Mazurkiewicz-Beldzinska M (2021) Nusinersen treatment of spinal muscular atrophy type 1 - results of expanded access programme in Poland. *Neurologia i Neurochirurgia Polska* 55: 289–294. <https://doi.org/10.5603/PJNNS.A2021.0020>
- Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, Antes G, Atkins D, Barbour V, Barrowman N, Berlin JA, Clark J, Clarke M, Cook D, D'Amico R, Deeks JJ, Devreux PJ, Dickersin K, Egger M, Ernst E, Gøtzsche PC, Grimshaw J, Guyatt G, Higgins J, Ioannidis JPA, Kleijnen J, Lang T, Magrini N, McNamee D, Moja L, Mulrow C, Napoli M, Oxman A, Pham B, Rennie D, Sampson M, Schulz KF, Shekelle PG, Tovey D, Tugwell P (2009) Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *PLOS Medicine* 6: e1000097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>
- Munsat T (1991) Workshop report: international SMA collaboration. *Neuromuscul Disord* 1: 81. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-8966\(91\)90052-t](https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-8966(91)90052-t) [June 12, 2025]
- NHS (2024) Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) - NHS. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/spinal-muscular-atrophy-sma/> [June 10, 2025]
- NICE (2021a) Onasemnogene abeparvec for treating spinal muscular atrophy Highly specialised technologies guidance. www.nice.org.uk/guidance/hst15
- NICE (2021b) Risdiplam for treating spinal muscular atrophy. www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta755
- NICE (n.d.) Nusinersen for treating spinal muscular atrophy | Guidance | NICE.
- Ñungo Garzón NC, Pitarch Castellano I, Sevilla T, Vázquez-Costa JF (2023) Risdiplam in non-sitter patients aged 16 years and older with 5q spinal muscular atrophy. *Muscle and Nerve* 67: 407–411. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mus.27804>
- Osmanovic A, Ranxha G, Kumpe M, Wurster CD, Stolte B, Cordts I, Günther R, Freigang M, Müschen LH, Binz C, Hermann A, Deschauer M, Lingor P, Ludolph AC, Hagenacker T, Schreiber-Katz O, Petri S (2021) Treatment satisfaction in 5q-spinal muscular atrophy under nusinersen therapy. *Therapeutic Advances in Neurological Disorders* 14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1756286421998902>
- Osredkar D, Jílková M, Butenko T, Loboda T, Golli T, Fuchsová P, Rohlenová M, Haberlova J (2021) Children and young adults with spinal muscular atrophy treated with nusinersen. *European Journal of Paediatric Neurology* 30: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpn.2020.11.004>
- Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, Shamseer L, Tetzlaff JM, Akl EA, Brennan SE, Chou R,

- Glanville J, Grimshaw JM, Hróbjartsson A, Lalu MM, Li T, Loder EW, Mayo-Wilson E, McDonald S, McGuinness LA, Stewart LA, Thomas J, Tricco AC, Welch VA, Whiting P, Moher D (2021) The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372: n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- Pane M, Coratti G, Sansone VA, Messina S, Bruno C, Catteruccia M, Sframeli M, Albamonte E, Pedemonte M, D'Amico A, Bravetti C, Berti B, Brigati G, Tacchetti P, Salmin F, de Sanctis R, Lucibello S, Piastra M, Genovese O, Bertini E, Vita G, Tiziano FD, Mercuri E (2019) Nusinersen in type 1 spinal muscular atrophy: Twelve-month real-world data. *Annals of Neurology* 86: 443–451. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.25533>
- Pane M, Berti B, Capasso A, Coratti G, Varone A, Amico AD, Messina S, Masson R, Sansone VA, Donati MA, Agosto C, Bruno C, Ricci F, Pini A, Gagliardi D, Filosto M, Corti S, Leone D, Palermo C, Onesimo R, De Sanctis R, Ricci M, Bitetti I, Sframeli M, Dosi C, Albamonte E, Ticci C, Brolatti N, Bertini E, Finkel R, Mercuri E (2023) Onasemnogene abeparvovec in spinal muscular atrophy: predictors of efficacy and safety in naïve patients with spinal muscular atrophy and following switch from other therapies. *eClinicalMedicine* 59: 101997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.101997>
- Patel A, Toro W, Yang M, Song W, Desai R, Ye M, Tabatabaepour N, Dabbous O (2024) Risk of utilization, adherence, and associated health care costs for patients with spinal muscular atrophy: a United States retrospective claims database analysis. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 19: 494. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-024-03399-0>
- PBAC (2022a) Public Summary Document – March 2022 PBAC Meeting. NUSINERSEN.
- PBAC (2022b) Public Summary Document - November 2022 PBAC Meeting. Onasemnogene Abeparvovec.
- PBAC (2024) Public Summary Document – July 2024 PBAC Meeting. RISDIPLAM.
- Pechmann A, Langer T, Schorling D, Stein S, Vogt S, Schara U, Kölbel H, Schwartz O, Hahn A, Giese K, Johannsen J, Denecke J, Weiß C, Theophil M, Kirschner J (2018) Evaluation of children with SMA Type 1 under treatment with nusinersen within the expanded access program in Germany. *Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases* 5: 135–143. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JND-180315>
- Pechmann A, Behrens M, Dörnbrack K, Tassoni A, Wenzel F, Stein S, Vogt S, Zöller D, Bernert G, Hagenacker T, Schara-Schmidt U, Walter MC, Steinbach M, Blaschek A, Baumann M, Baumgartner M, Becker B, Flotats-Bastardas M, Friese J, Günther R, Hahn A, Küpper H, Johannsen J, Kamm C, Koch JC, Köhler C, Kölbel H, Kolzter K, Von Moers A, Naegel S, Neuwirth C, Petri S, Rödiger A, Schimmel M, Schrank B, Schreiber G, Smitka M, Stadler C, Steiner E, Stögmänn E, Trollmann R, Türk M, Weiler M, Stoltenburg C, Willichowsky E, Zeller D, Ziegler A, Lochmüller H, Kirschner J (2023a) Improvements in walking distance during nusinersen treatment - a prospective 3-year SMARtCARE registry study. *Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases* 10: 29–40. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JND-221600>
- Pechmann A, Behrens M, Dörnbrack K, Tassoni A, Stein S, Vogt S, Zöller D, Bernert G, Hagenacker T, Schara-Schmidt U, Schwersenz I, Walter MC, Baumann M, Baumgartner M, Deschauer M, Eisenkölbl A, Flotats-Bastardas M, Hahn A, Horber V, Husain RA, Illsinger S, Johannsen J, Köhler C, Kölbel H, Müller M, von Moers A, Schlachter K, Schreiber G, Schwartz O, Smitka M, Steiner E, Stögmänn E, Trollmann R, Vill K, Weiß C, Wiegand G, Ziegler A, Lochmüller H, Kirschner J, Abele TB, Andres B, Angelova-Toshkina D, Baum P, Baum T, Baur U, Becker B, Behring B, Birsak T, Bellut J, Bertsche A, Blankenburg M, Blaschek A, Braun N, Braun S, Burgenmeister N, Claus N, Cordts I, de Vries H, Deba T, Della Marina A, Denecke J, Driemeyer J, Eckenweiler M, Fiedler B, Fischer M, Freigang M, Friese J, Gaiser P, Gebert A, Geitmann S, Goldhahn K, Grässl M, Gröning K, Grosskreutz J, Gruber-Sedlmayr U, Guillemot H, Günther R, von der Hagen M, Hartmann H, Hiebeler M, Hobbiebrunken E, Hoffmann GF, Holtkamp B, Holzwarth D, Jansen E, Kaindl A, Kaiser N, Klammroth J, Christoph Koch J, Koelker S, Kolzter K, Korschinsky B, Küpper H, Langer T, Lehnert I, Lingor P, Löscher WN, Loudovici-Krug D, Martakis K, Mayer I, Metelmann M, Meyer S, Mueller-Kaempffer K, Müller P, Müller-Felber W, Neuwirth C, Niederschweiberer J, Nolte A, Odorfer T, Omran H, Pauschek J, Pickrodt K, Plecko B, Pühringer M, Quinten AL, Rappold M, Reihle C, Reinhardt T, Rödiger A, Roetmann G, Saffari A, Schimmel M, Schneider J, Schoene-Bake C, Schorling D, Schwerin-Nagel A, Steinbach R, Steuernagel D, Stolte B, Stoltenburg C, Stüve B, Theophil M, Thiele S, Topakian R, Türk M, van der Stam L, Vollmann P, Warken B, Weber M, Weiler M, Weiss D, Weiss S, Wenzel F, Wider S, Wiebe N, Wilichowski E, Wilken B, Wochner K, Zeiner F, Zeisler D, Zeller D, Zemlin M (2023b) Effect of nusinersen on motor, respiratory and bulbar function in early-onset spinal muscular atrophy. *Brain* 146: 668–677. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awac252>
- Pechmann A, Behrens M, Dörnbrack K, Tassoni A, Wenzel F, Stein S, Vogt S, Zöller D, Bernert G, Hagenacker T, Schara-Schmidt U, Walter MC, Bertsche A, Vill K, Baumann M, Baumgartner M, Cordts I, Eisenkölbl A, Flotats-Bastardas M, Friese J, Günther R, Hahn A, Horber V, Husain RA, Illsinger S, Jahnel J, Johannsen J, Köhler C, Kölbel H, Müller M, von Moers A, Schwerin-Nagel A, Reihle C, Schlachter K, Schreiber G, Schwartz O, Smitka M, Steiner E, Trollmann R, Weiler M, Weiß C, Wiegand G, Wilichowski E, Ziegler A, Lochmüller H, Kirschner J, Ameshofer L, Andres B, Angelova-Toshkina D, Banholzer D, Bant C, Baum P, Baumann S, Baur U, Becker B, Behring B, Bellut J, Bevat A, Bischofberger J, Bitzan L, Bjelica B, Blankenburg M, Böger S, Bonetti F, Bongartz A, Brakemeier S, Bratka L, Braun N, Braun S, Brauner B, Bretschneider C, Burgenmeister N, Burke B, Cirak S, Dall A, de Vries H, Della MA, Denecke J, Deschauer M, Dibrani Z, Diebold U, Dondit L, Drebes J, Driemeyer J, Dukic V, Eckenweiler M, Eminger M, Fischer M, Fischer C, Freigang M, Gaiser P, Gangfuß A, Geitmann S, George A, Gosk-Tomek M, Grinzinger S, Gröning K, Groß M, Güttsches AK, Hagenmeyer A, Hartmann H, Haverkamp J, Hiebeler M, Hoevel A, Hoffmann GF, Holtkamp B, Holzwarth D, Homma A, Horneff V, Hörnig C, Hotter A, Hubert A, Huppke P, Jansen E, Jung L, Kaiser N, Kappel S, Katharina B, Koch J, Kölke S, Korschinsky B, Kostede F, Krause K, Küpper H, Lang A, Lange I, Langer T, Lechner Y, Lehmann H, Leybold C, Lingor P, Lipka J, Löscher W, Luiking A, Machetanz G, Malm E, Martakis K, Menzen B, Metelmann M, zu Hörste GM, Montagnese F, Mörtlbauer K, Müller P, Müller A, Müller A, Müschen L, Neuwirth C, Niesert M, Pauschek J, Pernegger E, Petri S, Pilshofer V, Plecko B, Pollok J, Preisel M, Pühringer M, Quinten AL, Raffler S, Ramadan B, Rappold M, Rauscher C, Reckmann K, Reinhardt T, Röder M, Roland-Schäfer D, Roth E, Ruß L, Saffari A, Schimmel M, Schlag M, Schlotter-Weigel B, Schneider J, Schöne-Bake JC, Schorling D, Schreiner I, Schüssler S, Schwarzbach M, Schwippert M, Semmler L, Smuda K, Sprenger-Svacina A, Stadler T, Steffens P, Steuernagel D, Stolte B, Stoltenburg C, Tasch G, Thimm A, Tiefenthaler E, Topakian R, Türk M, van der Stam L, Vettori K, Vollmann P, Vorgerd M, Weiss D, Wenninger S, Werring S, Wessel M, Weyen U, Wider S, Wiebe NO,

- Wiesenhofer A, Wiethoff S, Wirner C, Wohnrade C, Wunderlich G, Zeller D, Zemlin M, Zobel J (2022) Improved upper limb function in non-ambulant children with SMA type 2 and 3 during nusinersen treatment: a prospective 3-years SMARTCARE registry study. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-022-02547-8>
- Peña-Longobardo LM, Aranda-Reneo I, Oliva-Moreno J, Litzkendorf S, Durand-Zaleski I, Tizzano E, López-Bastida J (2020) The economic impact and health-related quality of life of spinal muscular atrophy. An analysis across Europe. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17: 5640. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17165640>
- Reyna S, Toro W, Patel A, Saleh S, Dabbous O (2024) 165P health care resource use (HCRU) for patients with spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) Types 2 or 3 in the UK. *Neuromuscular Disorders* 43: 104441.600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nmd.2024.07.609>
- Sansone VA, Pirola A, Albamonte E, Pane M, Lizio A, D'Amico A, Catteruccia M, Cutrera R, Bruno C, Pedemonte M, Messina S, Rao F, Roma E, Salmin F, Coratti G, Di Bari A, De Sanctis R, Pera CM, Sframeli M, Piastra M, Macagno F, Vita G, Bertini E, Mercuri E (2020) Respiratory needs in patients with type 1 spinal muscular atrophy treated with nusinersen. *Journal of Pediatrics* 219: 223-228.e4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2019.12.047>
- Scheijmans FEV, Cuppen I, van Eijk RPA, Wijngaarde CA, Schoenmakers MAGC, van der Woude DR, Bartels B, Veldhoen ES, Lansink ILBO, Groen EJM, Asselman F-L, Wadman RI, van der Pol WL (2022) Population-based assessment of nusinersen efficacy in children with spinal muscular atrophy: a 3-year follow-up study. *Brain Communications* 4. <https://doi.org/10.1093/braincomms/fcac269>
- Servais L (2024) Gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy: timing is key. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* 47: 101112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2024.101112>
- Servais L, Day JW, De Vivo DC, Kirschner J, Mercuri E, Muntoni F, Proud CM, Shieh PB, Tizzano EF, Quijano-Roy S, Desguerre I, Saito K, Faulkner E, Benguerba KM, Raju D, Lamarca N, Sun R, Anderson FA, Finkel RS (2024) Real-world outcomes in patients with spinal muscular atrophy treated with onasemnogene abeparvovec monotherapy: Findings from the RESTORE registry. *Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases* 11: 425-442. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JND-230122>
- Severa G, Alfaro M del C, Alimi Ichola C, Shoaito H, Souvannanorath S, Authier FJ, Malfatti E (2024) Risdiplam: therapeutic effects and tolerability in a small cohort of 6 adult type 2 and type 3 SMA patients. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 19: 430. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-024-03442-0>
- Shih STF, Farrar MA, Wiley V, Chambers G (2021) Newborn screening for spinal muscular atrophy with disease-modifying therapies: a cost-effectiveness analysis. *Journal of neurology, neurosurgery, and psychiatry* 92: 1296-1304. <https://doi.org/10.1136/JNNP-2021-326344>
- Sitas B, Hancevic M, Bilic K, Bilic H, Bilic E (2024) Risdiplam real world data – looking beyond motor neurons and motor function measures. *Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases* 11: 75. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JND-230197>
- Stettner GM, Hasselmann O, Tschertner A, Galiart E, Jacquier D, Klein A (2023) Treatment of spinal muscular atrophy with onasemnogene abeparvovec in Switzerland: a prospective observational case series study. *BMC Neurology* 23: 88. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-023-03133-6>
- Szabó L, Gergely A, Jakus R, Fogarasi A, Grosz Z, Molnár MJ, Andor I, Schulcz O, Goschler Á, Medveczky E, Czövek D, Herczegfalvi Á (2020) Efficacy of nusinersen in type 1, 2 and 3 spinal muscular atrophy: Real world data from Hungarian patients. *European Journal of Paediatric Neurology* 27: 37-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpn.2020.05.002>
- Thomas D, Hiligsmann M, John D, Al Ahdab OG, Li H (2019) Pharmacoeconomic analyses and modeling. *Clinical Pharmacy Education, Practice and Research: Clinical Pharmacy, Drug Information, Pharmacovigilance, Pharmacoeconomics and Clinical Research* 2019: 261-275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814276-9.00018-0>
- Tokatly Latzer I, Sagi L, Lavi R, Aharoni S, Bistrizter J, Noyman I, Ginsburg M, Lev-Or A, Katzenellenbogen S, Nevo Y, Fattal-Valevski A (2023) Real-Life Outcome After Gene Replacement Therapy for Spinal Muscular Atrophy: A Multicenter Experience. *Pediatric Neurology* 144: 60-68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pediatrneurol.2023.04.007>
- Trucco F, Ridout D, Weststrate H, Scoto M, Rohwer A, Coratti G, Main ML, Mayhew AG, Montes J, De Sanctis R, Pane M, Pera MC, Sansone VA, Albamonte E, D'Amico A, Bruno C, Messina SS, Childs AM, Willis T, Ong MT, Servais L, Majumdar A, Hughes I, Marini-Bettolo C, Parasuraman D, Gowda VL, Baranello G, Bertini ES, De Vivo DC, Darras BT, Day JW, Mayer O, Zolkipli-Cunningham Z, Finkel RS, Mercuri E, Muntoni F (2024) Therapeutic role of nusinersen on respiratory progression in pediatric patients with spinal muscular atrophy type 2 and nonambulant type 3. *Neurology: Clinical Practice* 14(3) e200298. <https://doi.org/10.1212/CPJ.0000000000200298>
- Valentini I, Ghetti G, Pane M, Cicchetti A, Rumi F, Di Brino E, Basile M, Pistillo G, Bischof M (2023) RWD129 cost effectiveness of onasemnogene abeparvovec in infants with presymptomatic spinal muscular atrophy in Italy. *Value in Health* 26: S528-S529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2023.09.2846>
- Verhaart IEC, Robertson A, Wilson IJ, Aartsma-Rus A, Cameron S, Jones CC, Cook SF, Lochmüller H (2017) Prevalence, incidence and carrier frequency of 5q-linked spinal muscular atrophy - A literature review. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 12: 124. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13023-017-0671-8>
- Vill K, Schwartz O, Blaschek A, Gläser D, Nennstiel U, Wirth B, Burggraf S, Röschinger W, Becker M, Czibere L, Durner J, Eggermann K, Olgemöller B, Harms E, Schara U, Kölbl H, Müller-Felber W (2021) Newborn screening for spinal muscular atrophy in Germany: clinical results after 2 years. *Orphanet journal of rare diseases* 16: 153. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13023-021-01783-8>
- Weiß C, Becker LL, Friese J, Blaschek A, Hahn A, Illsinger S, Schwartz O, Bernert G, Hagen M von der, Husain RA, Goldhahn K, Kirschner J, Pechmann A, Flotats-Bastardas M, Schreiber G, Schara U, Plecko B, Trollmann R, Horber V, Wilichowski E, Baumann M, Klein A, Eisenkölbl A, Köhler C, Stettner GM, Cirak S, Hasselmann O, Kaindl AM, Garbade SF, Johannsen J, Ziegler A, Baum P, Baumgartner M, Bertsche A, Blankenburg M, Denecke J, Deschauer M, Eckenweiler M, Geis T, Groß M, Günther R, Hagenacker T, Hamelmann E, Kamm C, Kauffmann B, Koch JC, Löscher W, Ludolph A, Martin P, Mensch A, Meyer zu Hörste G, Neuwirth C, Petri S, Pühringer M, Rathmann I, Schäfer D, Schimmel M, Schrank B, Schreiber-Katz O, Schwerin-Nagel A, Smitka M, Steinbach M, Steiner E, Stoffels J, Theophil M, Topakian R, Türk M, Vorgerd M, Walter MC, Weiler M, Wiegand G, Wunderlich G, Würster CD, Zeller D, Metelmann M, Zeiner F, Pilshofer V, Rappold M, Pauschek J, Reihle C, Homma AK, Lingor P, Henzi B, Reinhardt T, Holzwarth D, Wittmann W, Kappel S, Freigang M, Stolte B, Martakis

- K, Classen G, Roland-Schäfer D, Steuernagel D, Hartmann H, Fischer S, Wermuth M, Muhandes MT, Hotter A, Uzelac Z, Naegel S, Wiethoff S, Braun N, Bjelica B, Kölbel H, Angelova-Toshkina D, Wilken B, Osmanovic A, Fiedler B, Tomforde M, Voelkl T, von Moers A, Müller P, Behring B, Güttsches A, Reilich P, Wick W, Stoltenburg C, Witzel S, Bellut J, Hoffmann GF, Mörtlbauer K, Ille A, Schroth M, Driemeyer J, Semmler L, Müller C, Dörnbrack K, Zemlin M, Geitmann S, Lapp HS, Brakemeier S, Gehrke T, Ntemiris K, Kaiser N, Borowski S, Ramadan B, Hustedt U, Baum T, Schneider I, Akova-Oztürk E, Vill K, Dibrani Z, Wohnrade C, Della-Marina A, Jung L, Deba T, Zobel J, Schallner J, Kraut C, Vollmann P, Schüssler S, Roeder M, Hiebeler M, Berberich N, Schneider J, Brauner B, Kölker S, Pernegger E, Gosk-Tomek M, Braun S, Weiss D, Machetanz G, Langer T, Saier C, Baumann S, Hettrich S, Dworschak G, Müller-Kaempfer K, Dittes I, Thimm A, Quinten L, Albers K, Bevot A, Bretschneider C, Dorst J, Kendzierski T, Hannibal I, Bischofberger J, Riesmeier T, Gangfuß A, Johann to Settel E, Grässl M, Fiebig S, Hollerauer C, Seeber L, Krahwinkler I, Lange I, Montagnese F, Mann-Richter M, Wagner A, Leybold C, Saffari A, Anna E, Wiesenhofer A, Wendel EM, Steffens PS, Wider S, Tassoni A, Dall A, Busch F, Zeisler D, Wessel M, Lipka J, Hackemer A, Plugge L, Jansen E, Roth E, Schuster J, Koelsch A, Warken-Madelung B, Schwippert M, Holtkamp B, Köbbing K, Claeys S, Foerster S, Thiele S, Rochau-Trumpp H, George A, Niesert M, Neimair T, Vettori K, Haverkamp J, Taherpour J, Hug J, Wenzel F, Bant C, Baur U, Bühner K, Schlag M, Ruß L, Küpper H, Müller A, Wollinsky K, Well T, Leinert A, Andres B, Omran H, Claus N, Hagenmeyer A, Schnurr M, Dukic V, Ludolph AC, Specht S, Angermair V, Hüpper A, Banholzer D, Stein S, Kampowski T, Richmann M, Nicolai S, Atta O, Meßmer B, de Vries H, Rotenfusser E, Osmanovic A, Renger I, Guillemot H, Lehnert I, Grünwedel M, Grimm L, Stocker G, Hoevel A, Stadler T, Fischer M, Vogt S, Gebert A, Goldbach S, Lochmüller H, Müller-Felber W, Schara-Schmidt U, Probst-Schendzielorz K, Lang A, Nitzsche M, Hammer J, Müller-Kaempfer K, Wirner-Piotrowski C, van der Stam L, Bongartz A, Enzmann C, Fluss J, Galiart E, Jacquier D, Metzler DB, Tschertter A (2024) Efficacy and safety of gene therapy with onasemnogene abeparvovec in children with spinal muscular atrophy in the D-A-CH-region: a population-based observational study. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* 47: 101092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanpe.2024.101092>
- Wurster CD, Uzelac Z, Dreyhaupt J, Schuster J, Dorst J, Ludolph AC, Wollinsky K (2024) Respiratory function in adult patients with spinal muscular atrophy treated with nusinersen – a monocenter observational study. *Frontiers in Neurology* 15: 1372674. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2024.1372674>
- Xiao L, Chiang J, Castro-Codeçal M, Kolski H, Bedi P, Al Amrani F, Gonorazky HD, Amin R (2023) Respiratory characteristics in children with spinal muscular atrophy type 1 receiving nusinersen. *Pediatric Pulmonology* 58: 161–170. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppul.26173>
- Yao X, Peng J, Luo R, Wang X, Lu X, Wu L, Jin R, Zhong J, Liang J, Hong S, Yang L, Zhang X, Mao S, Hu J, Tao Z, Sun D, Wang H, Zhang L, Xia Y, Chen K, Wang Y (2024) Nusinersen effectiveness and safety in pediatric patients with 5q-spinal muscular atrophy: a multi-center disease registry in China. *Journal of Neurology* 271: 5378–5391. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-024-12442-w>
- Yeo CJJ, Simmons Z, Vivo DC De, Darras BT (2022) Ethical perspectives on treatment options with spinal muscular atrophy patients. *Annals of Neurology* 91: 305–316. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.26299>
- Yoon JA, Jeong Y, Lee J, Lee DJ, Lee KN, Shin YB (2024) Improvement in functional motor scores in patients with non-ambulatory spinal muscle atrophy during Nusinersen treatment in South Korea: a single center study. *BMC Neurology* 24: 210. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-024-03725-w>
- Zhao M, Ding S, Zhao Y, Lin C, Han Y (2025) Healthcare resource utilization, economic burden, and multi-level medical security system for individuals with spinal muscular atrophy in Shaanxi Province, China. *Healthcare (Switzerland)* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare13040428>
- Zhu C, Zaidman C, Youn B, Paradis AD, Raynaud S, Neville BA, Johnson NB (2024) Evaluation of inpatient and emergency department healthcare resource utilization and costs pre-and post-nusinersen for the treatment of spinal muscular atrophy using United States claims. *Journal of Comparative Effectiveness Research* 13: 7. <https://doi.org/10.57264/cer-2023-0187>
- Zuluaga-Sanchez S, Teynor M, Knight C, Thompson R, Lundqvist T, Ekelund M, Forsmark A, Vickers AD, Lloyd A (2019) Cost effectiveness of nusinersen in the treatment of patients with infantile-onset and later-onset spinal muscular atrophy in Sweden. *Pharmacoeconomics* 37: 845–865. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40273-019-00769-6>

Supplementary material 1

Real-world and economic outcomes in SMA

Authors: Neli Boseva-Stoyanova, Teodora Chamova, Guenka Petrova, Alexandra Savova

Data type: docx

Explanation note: The supplementary material includes detailed study-level tables supporting the findings of this systematic literature review. **table S1**. Presents the characteristics of the included real-world studies. **tables S2–S8**. Summarise the extracted outcomes by domain. **tables S9–S11**. Present the included economic evaluations by therapy.

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e195536.suppl1>